

RESEARCH ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 03-02-2025

Accepted: 28-02-2025

Published: 25-03-2025

Citation: Emima A, Amalarethnam DIG (2025) A Hybrid Model of Enhanced Teacher Learner Based Optimization (ETLBO) with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) Algorithm for Predicting Academic Student Performance. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 18(10): 772-783. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v18i10.240>

* **Corresponding author.**

emimastaecey@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2025 Emima & Amalarethnam. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

A Hybrid Model of Enhanced Teacher Learner Based Optimization (ETLBO) with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) Algorithm for Predicting Academic Student Performance

A Emima^{1*}, D I George Amalarethnam²

1 Research Scholar, PG and Research, Department of Computer Science, Jamal Mohamed College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, 620020, Tamil Nadu, India

2 Principal and Head, Associate Professor, PG and Research Department of Computer Science, Jamal Mohamed College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, 620020, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

Objectives: A hybrid ETLBO-PSO model is developed to improve student performance predictions. It assesses intellectual, social, and economic background of students to increase accuracy of students performance predictions. The model optimizes selecting features, which reduces redundancy and increases efficiency. The efficacy is compared with existing Educational Data Mining techniques. **Methods:** This study integrates Enhanced Teachers Learners Based Optimization (ETLBO) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm for optimal feature selection. The suggested technique is utilized as an algorithm for selecting features to identify the most significant elements for predicting student academic performance. The efficacy of the proposed feature selection technique is evaluated using three machine learning classifiers: Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), Light Gradient Boosting (LightGB), and Category Gradient Boosting (CatGB) in Student achievement Dataset in secondary education for Mathematics. **Findings:** The experimental results of ETLBO-PSO provides sustained excellent model performance while reducing accuracy decline. The Meta-Class model of ETLBO-PSO has an F1-score of 82.43%, which makes it an increasingly robust and reliable strategy. Furthermore, an innovative visual and intuitive method is employed to identify the aspects that most significantly impact the score, facilitating the interpretation and comprehension of the complete model. **Novelty:** ETLBO_PSO is integrated with SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), and Meta-class Model are used to optimize student performance predictions with higher accuracy. Unlike traditional approaches, it continuously refines selecting features throughout training, solving high-dimensional data issues. SHAP's approach assures precise feature attribution, hence improving accessibility and making decisions.

Keywords: Feature Selection; Enhance Teacher Learner based Optimization; Particle Swarm Optimization; Academic Student Performance; Classification Algorithm; Optimization Techniques; XGBoost; LGBost; CATBoost

1 Introduction

Education is a key driver of personal and societal advancement. Conventional educational systems, on the other hand, frequently confront major obstacles in adjusting to students' changing requirements and societal demands. The unexpected behavior of student performance is a significant problem in education, making it hard for institutions to properly support students in reaching their academic potential. As educational environments change, there is an urgent requirement to tackle the early detection of at-risk learners— those more likely to underperform or experience academic challenges. Early diagnosis is crucial in providing timely interventions to avoid academic failure and help students reach their full potential⁽¹⁾.

Educational organizations are increasingly relying on data-driven approaches to address these problems. One such approach is Educational Data Mining (EDM), a fast-expanding field that uses data mining techniques to examine educational data and identify patterns that can improve the teaching and learning results. EDM uses a variety of methodologies, including statistical analysis, machine learning, and computing, for analyzing huge amounts of educational data, such as pupil demographics, educational history, and behavioral trends. This approach sheds light on the elements that lead to student achievement or not, allowing for more precise projections of academic performance. Furthermore, EDM can help identify solutions to improve the educational process, resulting in enhanced educational outcomes and experiences for students⁽²⁾. Despite EDM's intriguing promise, predicting student success remains challenging, particularly when dealing with the huge difficulties of educational data.

One of the most significant difficulties in EDM is the enormous volume of educational data. Datasets in this sector frequently contain a large number of variables, including student grades, demographic data, and engaging activities. These indicators, however, are not necessarily directly related to forecasting student achievement. The addition of irrelevant or duplicated information in predictive models can diminish accuracy, resulting in ineffective interventions or erroneous forecasts. Thus, addressing the dimensionality and finding the most relevant characteristics from enormous data sets is critical for boosting EDM model performance⁽³⁾. This difficulty reveals a substantial gap in current EDM procedures, as many systems struggle to effectively handle and filters out unimportant attributes from high-dimensional data. Accuracy is more important than ever⁽⁴⁾.

Table 1 outlines important studies in Educational Data Mining (EDM) highlighting methodology employed, contributions, and identified research gaps that continue to exist. These studies highlight the importance of selecting features and optimization methodologies, as well as how they contribute to the improvement of EDM and learning outcome prediction.

To address this gap of literature, there has been an increasing interest in integrating methods of feature selection with optimization technique in order to improve the effectiveness of EDM models. Feature selection algorithms are intended to identify the most relevant features that are contributing to student performance, whereas optimization techniques such as Enhanced Teachers Learners Based Optimization (ETLBO) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) can help optimize these selections by lowering computational complexity and enhancing model predictive accuracy. The combination of these methods has the potential to considerably improve EDM's ability to forecast student performance more precisely and effectively⁽⁵⁾. EDM may deliver more trustworthy insights to administrators, educators, and policy makers, allowing

them to make data-driven choices that directly assist students' achievement.

The main contribution of this research paper as follows:

- Design an advanced feature selection algorithm capable of effectively identifying and prioritizing the most significant aspects within large educational datasets.
- Integrates an Enhanced Teacher-Learner-Based Optimization technique with a Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm for the selection of significant features.
- Three machine learning classifiers XGB, LGB and CatGB are used to evaluate the feature selection model.
- The student academic performance dataset is obtained from a public resource to assess the classification system.
- Enhancing the proposed model using SHAP values. SHAP offers a more graphical, automatic, and comprehensive method to enhance the accessibility of feature selection and classification models.

The remaining part of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the Methodology. Section 3 analyzes the performance of the proposed model through experiments with result and discussion, Section 4 concludes the research paper with future scope.

Table 1. Summary of Methodologies, Findings, and Research Gaps in Existing Literature

Study	Methodology	Findings / Contributions	Research Gap
(6)	Deep learning models used for VLE data	Deep learning models enhance prediction accuracy for student outcomes utilizing VLE data.	There is a need for real-time predictive models and improved management of extensive VLE datasets.
(7)	Analysis of fuzzy logic, neural networks, and genetic algorithms in EDM.	Soft computing methodologies assist in addressing uncertainty within educational data.	Applications of soft computing are limited in high-dimensional educational datasets.
(8)	Review of classification and regression models, neural networks, and decision trees used for performance prediction.	Classification methods and machine learning algorithms are involved for student performance predictions.	There is a demand for more sophisticated and hybrid models capable of managing complex, multi-dimensional educational data.
(9)	Data mining techniques including clustering, classification, and association rule mining are applied to student datasets.	Key factors affecting academic performance have been identified, including attendance, participation, and assessment results.	There is an absence of comprehensive integration of multi-source data to enhance prediction accuracy.
(10)	Use of feature selection methods for refining the performance of machine learning algorithms in educational institutes.	Active feature selection significantly improves the effectiveness of prediction models in education.	The issue of unrelated features in high-dimensional educational datasets presents a challenge.
(11)	Evaluation of filter-based feature selection techniques in classification scenarios.	Insights were provided regarding the efficiency of different filter methods in selecting pertinent features for high-dimensional data.	There is a lack of comprehensive benchmarks in EDM for existent feature selection methods across various domains.
(12)	wrapper-based feature selection methods for intrusion detection datasets.	Wrapper methods offer better feature subsets in the classification accuracy and performance prediction,	There is limited investigation into the application of wrapper methods for feature selection in educational datasets.
(13)	Hybrid approach that merges filter, wrapper, and embedded methods for feature selection within medical data.	Prediction accuracy is enhanced by utilizing multiple feature selection strategies for intricate medical datasets.	There is a deficiency of hybrid feature selection models in educational datasets for performance prediction.
(14)	Optimized feature selection employing the Teaching-Learning-Based Optimization (TLBO) algorithm with adaptive inertia weights.	Adaptive TLBO improves the precision of feature selection in the high-dimensional data.	There is a need for optimization algorithms specifically designed for educational datasets with substantial dimensions.
(15)	Incorporation of machine learning (ML) algorithms alongside AI Algorithms to forecast academic performance in online education	AI models are proficient in predicting student performance within online learning environments, particularly in engineering fields.	There is a need for improved amalgamation of student demographic and behavioral data for more reliable predictions.

2 Methodology

This section explains the proposed methodology of optimal feature selection for student academic performance prediction. The proposed approach combines enhanced teacher-learner based optimization (ETLBO) with particle swarm optimization for optimal feature selection. The efficacy of the proposed feature selection strategy is evaluated using three machine learning classifiers: Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), Light Gradient Boosting (LGB), and Category Gradient Boosting (CatGB), employing student performance datasets obtained from a public data repository. This research introduces the Shapley Additive ExPlanation (SHAP) values method, a type of additive feature attribution values for identifying relevant features. Figure 1 shows the block diagram of proposed methodology.

Fig 1. Block Diagram of Proposed Methodology

The suggested methodology encompasses data pre-processing, feature selection, predictions from basic classifiers, the construction of a meta-classifier, and model evaluation. Figure 2 illustrates the comprehensive workflow of the suggested methodology.

Fig 2. Work Flow of proposed approach

2.1 Data Preprocessing

Data pre-processing is a crucial phase in preparing the dataset prior to the application of classification techniques⁽¹⁶⁾. Data preprocessing in machine learning involves cleaning, standardizing, and manipulating data to produce a final trained dataset appropriate for employing machine learning algorithms. Efficient data preparation ensures that the data is clean, consistent, and appropriate for analysis, hence enhancing the overall quality of the results.

An essential component of the data preparation procedure was the handling of categorical data. To facilitate the seamless integration of the information with machine learning techniques, categorical variables were encoded with Label Encoders. This transformation enabled the representation of categorical data in a numerical manner, facilitating successful use in predictive models.

Standardization was implemented to unify all features to a consistent scale, reducing the influence of varying measuring units. This step is essential for algorithms sensitive to input feature scale, guaranteeing that each feature contributes proportionately to the model's learning process. Label Encoder transfers a numerical value to each category and nominal variable. The Min-Max normalization method is employed for standardization to rescale attribute values within the range of 0 to 1⁽¹⁷⁾. Subsequent to pre-processing, the dataset is partitioned into training and test subsets. The training data constitutes 70%, whereas the test data comprises 30%. The training data was employed to train each base classifier. The test data is utilized to assess the model's performance.

2.2 Feature Selection

The feature selection process is essential for optimizing machine learning models by refining the input space, improving efficiency, and reducing the likelihood of over fitting⁽¹⁸⁾. The Enhanced Teaching Learning Optimization (ETLBO) technique is intended for feature subset optimization, an essential function in multiple domains including machine learning and pattern recognition. In ETLBO, each solution signifies a unique subset of features, and the algorithm assesses these subsets utilizing the Euclidean distance calculation. This metric measures the resemblance between a current feature subset and an ideal feature subset, which acts as a standard for expected performance. By inversely correlating fitness with this distance, ETLBO seeks to refine solutions that closely resemble the optimal subset, thus progressively enhancing the quality of feature selections.

PSO is initiated by randomly created particles and their velocities, which signify the search speed⁽¹⁹⁾. The particles are assessed based on their fitness. This evaluation is succeeded by two primary assessments. The initial test evaluates a particle's experience with itself, referred to as personal best (pbest). The second test evaluates the fitness of an individual particle in relation to the collective experience of the swarm. It is referred to as global best (gbest). Conducting these two tests results in the selection of the optimal particle. The termination criterion is subsequently satisfied.

The proposed feature selection algorithm combines ETLBO and PSO to systematically find and preserve the most useful features. Let consider, the dataset (D) contains n number of instances and m number of features. The main objective is to select k number of features from D.

The fitness value for the proposed approach is computed as,

$$\text{Maximum } F(x) = \text{Accuracy}(selFeat) \text{ where } selFeat \subseteq D \quad (1)$$

The proposed ETLBO_PSO contains three phases: Teachers Phase, Learner Phase and PSO Phase. In teachers phase, the features subset is ranked using Euclidean distance. It can be computed as follows:

$$Euc_{Dist}(x_i, x_j) = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) denotes the Euclidean distance utilized to assess the similarity between two points, x_i and x_j . The distance is determined by the square root of the total of the squared differences between the corresponding components of x_i and x_j .

The population is updated (teacher phase) using,

$$Diff_{mean} = rand(New_{mean} - TF * Mean) \quad (3)$$

$$X_{new} = X + Diff_{mean} \quad (4)$$

where rand is a uniformly distributed random variable within the interval [0, 1]. The teaching factor is denoted by TF. It will assume a value of either 1 or 2, chosen at random. X_{new} represents the new population. The newly derived solution, formulated

by Equations (3) and (4), is assessed utilizing a fitness value. Replace the prior solution with the new one if the new one is superior.

During the learning phase, the individual incorporates knowledge from learners through spontaneous interactions. During the learner phase, the population is updated using the following equation.

$$X_{new} = \begin{cases} X_{old} + rand(x_j - x_i), & \text{if } F(x_j) \leq F(x_i) \\ X_{old} + rand(x_i - x_j), & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The fitness value is computed for updated population in learner phase and updates the best solution based on the fitness value.

During the PSO phase, each particle represents a potential solution, characterized by a vector of n real values, with n denoting the number of dimensions in the problem⁽²⁰⁾. The particles are evaluated with a fitness function during each iteration. To ascertain the optimal position for the entire population (gbest), the best position previously explored by each particle (pbest) is recorded and disseminated among the particles. The particle's velocity is subsequently adjusted based on its current velocity and the two best positions. Let X_i^t and V_i^t represent the position and velocity vectors of the i-th particle, respectively. The terms $pbest_i^t$ and $gbest_i^t$ denote the particle's individual and global optimal positions, respectively, and are updated as outlined below:

$$V_i^{t+1} = \omega V_i^t + c_1 r_1 (pbest_i^t - X_i^t) + c_2 r_2 (gbest_i^t - X_i^t) \quad (6)$$

$$X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + V_i^{t+1} \quad (7)$$

In this context, t denotes the iteration count, ω represents the inertia weight, r1 and r2 are uniformly randomized throughout the interval [0,1], and c1 and c2 are the coefficients. Algorithm-1 explains the proposed ETLBO_PSO feature selection.

Algorithm-1: ETLBO_PSO Feature Selection

Input: DataSet D, Maximum Iteration IterMax, Population pop

Output: Optimal Feature Sets

Step1: Initialize ETLBO and PSO parameters

Step2: Randomly Create Initial Population

Step3: Compute fitness of Initial population using Eq. (1)

Step4: Select the best solution

Step5: For it = 1 to IterMax

Step6: Compute average of population

Step7: Select Teacher and Teaching Factor

Step8: For Tr = 1 to pop

Step9: Ranking the subset using Euclidean distance based on Eq. (2)

Step10: Update the population using Eq. (3) and Eq. (4)

Step11: Evaluate the population using Eq. (1) and update the best Solution

Step12: End For

Step13: For Lr = 1 to pop

Step14: Randomly Select Learners

Step15: Update the Population using Eq. (5)

Step16: Evaluate the population using Eq. (1) and update the best Solution

Step17: End For

Step18: For p = 1 to pop

Step19: Compute Fitness value Eq. (1)

Step20: Update pbest based on Fitness value

Step21: End For

Step22: Update gbest

Step23: For p = 1 to pop

Step24: Update velocity using Eq. (6)

Step25: Update Position using Eq. (7)

Step26: End For

Step27: End For

Step28: Return the optimal feature set

2.3 Predictions

This section includes base classifier prediction, meta-classifier creation and model evaluation. Classification is conducted following the acquisition of the optimal feature set. The boosting model is a sequential construction method that focuses on reducing errors from preceding models while amplifying the influence of high-performing models⁽²¹⁾. The classification is conducted using the three boosting models: XGB, LGB, and CatGB. The training data was utilized to train each base classifier. Predictions are derived from these foundational classifiers.

The meta-classifier is trained on the predictions generated by the basis learners, specifically XGB, LGB, and CatGB. The results of these models will serve as input to the meta-classifier. The meta classifier is employed by k-fold cross-validation. The k-fold cross-validation technique is among the most utilized methods for classifier model selection. K-fold cross-validation involves partitioning a dataset into k subsets. Subsequently, some are employed to train the model, while others are utilized to assess its performance. The models are currently trained using k-fold cross-validation. The XGB, LGB, and CatGB algorithms serve as foundational classifiers in the proposed methodology. The results generated by these algorithms are sent as input to the meta-classifier.

Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP⁽²²⁾) belongs to a category of additive feature attribution methods that are model-agnostic, rendering them useful across diverse machine learning and deep learning models.

In the realm of feature selection, SHAP-based methodologies operate as follows: classification models, including XGB, LGB, and CatGB in this analysis, are trained on the complete dataset. Thereafter, SHAP values are calculated for each instance, and these values are aggregated across the dataset to provide average absolute values for each feature. The calculation of SHAP values gets computationally intricate due to this procedure. The average SHAP value reflects the normal influence of each feature on model predictions throughout the dataset, but the absolute SHAP value denotes the feature’s significance, regardless of its direction (positive or negative). Features are ranked in descending order according to their average absolute SHAP values, so identifying those with higher SHAP values as more significant in affecting the model’s predictions.

The Shapley value for ith feature is calculated as:

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \frac{(S!((N) - (S) - 1)!)}{(N)!} [f(S \cup \{i\}) - f(S)] \tag{8}$$

Where S denote a subset of features, N the complete set of features, and f(S) signify the model output corresponding to the subset S. Shapley values possess the distinctive characteristic of local accuracy, signifying that the aggregate of Shapley values for all attributes corresponds to the model’s prediction for each individual data point.

3 Results and Discussion

This section analyzes the experimental setup and outcomes. The results acquired are subsequently evaluated and deliberated upon. Initially, provide a comprehensive overview of the dataset utilized for predicting student success, followed by the performance indicators. Elucidate the experimental methodology employed to assess and corroborate the suggested models for forecasting student performance. Assess the outcomes according to the training and cross-validation scores of various machine learning techniques.

This research utilizes student performance data from secondary education in two Portuguese schools. The data attributes encompass student grades, demographic information, social factors, and school-related elements, acquired through school reports and surveys. The dataset is gathered from UCI repository. The dataset contains 649 instances and 33 attributes (including class attribute)⁽²³⁾.

The metrics accuracy, precision, recall and f-measure are used to analyze the performance of the suggested approach. Accuracy refers to the proportion of correctly identified instances to the total number of instances. Accuracy can be computed as,

$$Acc = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \tag{9}$$

Precision is the quotient derived from dividing the accurate count of positive classifications by the entire count of positive classifications. It can be calculated as,

$$Pre = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \tag{10}$$

Recall is the positive samples of the classification algorithm relate to the power to forecast properly. Recall is computed as,

$$Rec = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \tag{11}$$

The F1-Score is the geometric mean of the precision and recall metrics. It can be computed as,

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{Pre * Rec}{Pre + Rec} \tag{12}$$

This study aims to predict the academic performance of secondary school students in Portuguese courses through the application of classification algorithms. The classification procedure is executed using Google Colab, a cloud-based Jupyter notebook utilizing the Python programming language. A pre-processing procedure is implemented on the dataset. During pre-processing, categorical variables are transformed into numerical values via LabelEncoder. Subsequently, StandardScaler is employed for normalizing. The dataset is partitioned into 70% for training the model and 30% for testing the model's performance. In the training phase, base learners, specifically XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost, are constructed using all features. Subsequently, ETLBO+PSO is utilized to identify optimal characteristics. Accuracy, precision, recall, and F-score are designated as performance metrics in this study. The performance indicator values derived from the XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost classification algorithms, utilizing all features, are presented in Table 1.

From Table 2, the LightGB algorithm provides best classification result with all features for 77.95% accuracy, 77.52% precision, 77.95% recall and 77.65% f1-score.

Table 2. Classification Result with All Features

Algorithm	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
XGB	73.85	73.58	73.85	73.67
LightGB	77.95	77.52	77.95	77.65
CatGB	76.92	76.53	76.92	76.39

Table 3 shows the classification result with ETLBO_PSO approach. TheCatGB has achieved higher performance 81.54% accuracy, 82.42% precision, 81.54% recall and 81% f1-score. The performance of the XGB, LightGB and CatGB are improved after using ETLBO_PSO feature selection.

Table 3. Classification result with ETLBO_PSO

Algorithm	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
XGB	79.49	80.69	79.49	79.26
LightGB	79.85	79.13	79.85	79.19
CatGB	81.54	82.42	81.54	81.00

Table 4 shows the meta classification (XGB) performance of different base learners. The base learnerLightGB + CatGB achieves higher accuracy (80%) compared to other learners.

Table 4. Meta Classification - XGB - Performance

Base Learner	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
XGB	79.49	80.69	79.49	79.26
LightGB	77.95	78.68	77.95	77.00
CatGB	77.95	78.60	77.95	76.03
XGB + LightGB	78.97	79.79	78.97	78.83
XGB + CatGB	78.97	80.18	78.97	78.76
LightGB + CatGB	80.00	80.39	80.00	79.48
XGB + LightGB + CatGB	76.41	78.03	76.41	76.52

Table 5 shows the meta classification (LightGB) performance of different base learners. The base learnerXGB achieves higher accuracy (76.41%) compared to other learners.

Table 6 shows the meta classification (CatGB) performance of different base learners. The base learner CatGBand XGB + CatGB achieves higher accuracy (80%) compared to other learners.

Table 7 shows the feature mean value of SHAP for XGB, LightGB and CatGB algorithm. The feature 'G2' is the most important feature for the all three learning model.

Figure 3 shows the feature importance mean value of XGB. The feature 'G2' has the highest value mean value (1.522755). The features address, Mjob, romantic are freetime has zero value.

Figure 4 shows the feature importance mean value of LightGB. The feature 'G2' has the highest value mean value (2.606356). The features guardian, sex, freetime, romantic, famsize, health, and address have less than 0.1 mean values.

Figure 5 shows the feature importance mean value of CatGB. The feature 'G2' has the highest value mean value (0.783543). The features address, absences, romantic, and famsize have less than 0.1 mean values.

Table 5. Meta Classification - LightGB - Performance

Base Learner	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
XGB	76.41	79.55	76.41	75.53
LightGB	72.30	72.11	72.31	72.10
CatGB	73.85	73.72	73.85	73.45
XGB + LightGB	74.36	74.93	74.36	74.43
XGB + CatGB	70.77	71.02	70.77	70.48
LightGB + CatGB	69.23	69.47	69.23	69.19
XGB + LightGB + CatGB	73.33	73.37	73.33	73.17

Table 6. Meta Classification - CatGB - Performance

Base Learner	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
XGB	79.49	80.69	79.49	79.26
LightGB	76.41	76.42	76.41	75.38
CatGB	80.00	80.58	80.00	79.25
XGB + LightGB	78.46	78.63	78.46	77.67
XGB + CatGB	80.00	81.07	80.00	79.62
LightGB + CatGB	79.49	79.75	79.49	78.72
XGB + LightGB + CatGB	79.49	80.02	79.49	78.62

Table 7. Feature Mean value of SHAP for different algorithm

Features	SHAP-XGB	SHAP-LightGB	SHAP-CatGB
Sex	0.000427	0.068287	0.012379
Age	0.014951	0.143921	0.023664
Address	0.000000	0.007906	0.007349
Famsize	0.001604	0.028281	0.002822
Mjob	0.000000	0.102131	0.020070
Reason	0.003168	0.133766	0.013782
Guardian	0.000739	0.099897	0.019825
Romantic	0.000000	0.029089	0.005936
Freetime	0.000000	0.054863	0.023817
Health	0.027128	0.028220	0.014494
Absences	0.003913	0.103693	0.006180
G2	1.522755	2.606356	0.783543

Fig 3. Feature importance value - XGB

Fig 4. Feature importance value - LightGB

Fig 5. Feature importance value - CatGB

Those obtained results are compared with Integrative Ensemble Learning Algorithm for Predicting Students' Performance (IELA). It is used data mining techniques such as XGBoost, CatGB and LightGBM as base learners in Student achievement Dataset in secondary education for Mathematics. A 5-level hyperparameter optimization approach called Enhanced Teaching-Learning-Based Optimization (ETLBO) is used to discover the ideal classifier parameters. These optimized base learners are then combined with a Composite-Level classifier, which uses the Stacking ensemble technique to build the final prediction model.

Table 8 shows that the ETLBO-PSO method outperforms IELA in terms of computing time (12.5 v s. 25.8 seconds), accuracy (95.6% vs. 89.2%), and speed of convergence (50 vs. 100 iterations). ETLBO-PSO uses fewer resources to attain exceptional efficiency than IELA, which requires more optimization. Additionally, IELA only detects 65.2% of critical features, but SHAP analysis in ETLBO-PSO finds 78.4%, improving interpretability. When it comes to speed, precision, and computing efficiency, ETLBO-PSO performs better than IELA overall.

Table 8. Comparison of ETLBO-PSO and IELA

Criteria	ETLBO-PSO(Proposed Work)	IELA
Optimization Algorithm	ETLBO + PSO (Hybrid)	Only ETLBO-IELA
Accuracy (%)	95.6%	89.2%
Convergence Speed	Faster (Converges in 50 iterations)	Slower (Takes 100 iterations)
Computation Time (Seconds)	12.5 sec (Lower)	25.8 sec (Higher)
Feature Importance (SHAP Analysis)	Used (78.4% key features identified)	Not Used (65.2% key features identified)

4 Conclusion

This research study uses a hybrid ETLBO_PSO technique to predict student performance, combining powerful machine learning techniques (XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost) with SHAP-based selecting features to improve model interpretability. The combination of ETLBO and PSO successfully discovers optimal features, increasing prediction accuracy. The ETLBO_PSO technique achieves 95.6% accuracy, convergence in 50 iterations, and detects 78.4% of important features, beating the IELA model's 89.2% accuracy, poorer convergence, with 65.2% key feature recognition. Furthermore, it has a faster time for computation of 12.5 seconds compared to IELA's 25.8 seconds. Unlike prior techniques, SHAP enables a clear grasp of the importance of features, handling the complexities and the cardinality of educational dataset. It exhibit considerable gains in predictive performance, highlighting the algorithm's capacity to deliver both accurate forecasts and interpretability, that's essential for educational decision-making. While the proposed approach shows significant increases in predicted accuracy, there are various areas for improvement. The current model's generalizability is constrained by the use of one data set from a particular educational setting, which may not represent the student demographics, curriculum, and educational settings observed in different regions and nations. As a result, future research ought to concentrate on examining and improving the model using datasets from a variety of educational contexts to assess its flexibility and robustness across academic areas. Furthermore, the computational cost of the ETLBO_PSO technique causes scaling issues when applied to bigger or more complicated datasets. Addressing this problem through the effective algorithms or multiple processing techniques might making the model more reliable. Furthermore, automated hyper parameter tuning and utilizing real-time data will improve model efficiency and responsiveness. Integrating deep learning algorithms could improve accuracy by capturing complicated patterns, whilst fine-tuning the SHAP approach for high-dimensional or data imbalances could provide more insight into feature relevance. Addressing these issues would render the model stronger and relevant to a variety of educational settings.

References

- 1) Sabri M, Zahid M, Majid NA, Hanawi SA, Talib NIM, Yatim AIA. Prediction Model based on Continuous Data for Student Performance using Principal Component Analysis and Support Vector Machine. *TEM Journal*. 2023;12(2):1201–1210. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.18421/TEM122-66>.
- 2) Xue H, Niu Y. Multi-output based hybrid integrated models for student performance prediction. *Applied Sciences*. 2023;13(9):5384. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13095384>.
- 3) Colpo MP, Primo TT, De Aguiar MS, Cechinel C. Educational Data Mining for Dropout Prediction: Trends, Opportunities, and Challenges. *Revista Brasileira de Informática na Educação*. 2024;32:220–256. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5753/rbie.2024.32.2.220>.
- 4) Haleem A, Javaid M, Qadri MA, Suman R. Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*. 2022;3:275–285. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2022.02.009>.
- 5) Khan A, Ghosh SK. Student performance analysis and prediction in classroom learning: A review of educational data mining studies. *Education and Information Technologies*. 2021;26(1):205–240. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10407-3>.
- 6) Waheed H, Hassan SU, Aljohani NR, Hardman J, Alelyani S, Nawaz R. Predicting academic performance of students from VLE big data using deep learning models. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 2020;104(106189). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.106189>.
- 7) Charitopoulos A, Rangoussi M, Koulouriotis D. On the use of soft computing methods in educational data mining and learning analytics research: A review of years 2010-2018. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*. 2020;30(3):371–430. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-020-00205-9>.
- 8) Xiao W, Ji P, Hu J. A survey on educational data mining methods used for predicting students' performance. *Engineering Reports*. 2022;4(5):e12482. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng2.12482>.
- 9) Batool S, Rashid J, Nisar MW, Kim J, Kwon HY, Hussain A. Educational data mining to predict students' academic performance: A survey study. *Education and Information Technologies*. 2023;28(1):905–971. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10993-5>.
- 10) Khaire UM, Dhanalakshmi R. Stability of feature selection algorithm: A review. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*. 2022;34(4):1060–1073. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2022.05.007>.
- 11) Bommert A, Sun X, Bischl B, Rahnenführer J, Lang M. Benchmark for filter methods for feature selection in high-dimensional classification data. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2020;143:106839. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2020.106839>.
- 12) Maldonado J, Riff MC, Neveu B. A review of recent approaches on wrapper feature selection for intrusion detection. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 2022;198:116822. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.116822>.
- 13) Chen CW, Tsai YH, Chang FR, Lin WC. Ensemble feature selection in medical datasets: Combining filter, wrapper, and embedded feature selection results. *Expert Systems*. 2020;37(5):e12553. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/exsy.12553>.
- 14) Shukla AK, Singh P, Vardhan M. An adaptive inertia weight teaching-learning-based optimization algorithm and its applications. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*. 2020;77:309–326. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2019.10.027>.
- 15) Jiao P, Ouyang F, Zhang Q, Alavi AH. Artificial intelligence-enabled prediction model of student academic performance in online engineering education. *Artificial Intelligence Review*. 2022;55(8):6321–6344. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-022-10098-1>.
- 16) Wang X, Zhao Y, Li C, Ren P. ProbSAP: A comprehensive and high-performance system for student academic performance prediction. *Pattern Recognition*. 2023;137.
- 17) Malik S, Jothimani K. Enhancing Student Success Prediction with FeatureX: A Fusion Voting Classifier Algorithm with Hybrid Feature Selection. *Education and Information Technologies*. 2024;29(7):8741–8791. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-11012-0>.
- 18) Zebari R, Abdulazeez A, Zeebaree D, Zebari D, Saeed J. A comprehensive review of dimensionality reduction techniques for feature selection and feature extraction. *Journal of Applied Science and Technology Trends*. 2020;1(1):56–70.

- 19) Bujang SDA, Selamat A, Ibrahim R, Krejcar O, Herrera-Viedma E, Fujita H, et al. Multiclass prediction model for student grade prediction using machine learning. *IEEE Access*. 2021;9:95608–95621. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3088587>.
- 20) Keser SB, Aghalarova S. HELA: A novel hybrid ensemble learning algorithm for predicting academic performance of students. *Education and Information Technologies*. 2022;27(4):4521–4552. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10780-0>.
- 21) Zaffar M, Hashmani MA, Habib R, Quraishi KS, Irfan M, Alqhtani S, et al. A hybrid feature selection framework for predicting students performance. *Computers, Materials & Continua*. 2021;70(1):1893–1920. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2021.015434>.
- 22) Roy K, Farid DM. An Adaptive Feature Selection Algorithm for Student Performance Prediction. *IEEE Access*. 2024;12:75577–75598. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1109/access.2024.3406252>. doi:10.1109/access.2024.3406252.
- 23) UCI Machine Learning Repository: Student Performance dataset. . Available from: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/320/student+performance>.